

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF THE PRESERVATION STATE OF REPETITION SKILLS IN SENSORY APHASIA

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Abstract. This article analyzes the results of an experiment on the preservation of repetition ability in patients whose native language is Uzbek and who have lost comprehension ability due to sensory aphasia. The ability to repeat is characteristic of several types of aphasia, and its theoretical aspects have been studied in foreign scientific sources. In our experiment, impaired repetition skills were also observed in sensory aphasia. It was noted that the impairment occurs at the level of non-semantic words. This supports A. Luria's views that the deficiency in sensory aphasia arises from damage to the part of the brain's left hemisphere in the upper temporal region that serves for phonological differentiation.

Keywords: *aphasia, speech disorders, linguistic skills, lexical route model, non-lexical route model, dual-route model, A. Luria, computer modeling, semantic nodes.*

INTRODUCTION.

Research on aphasia notes that three main criteria are taken into account when describing and classifying aphasic syndromes: fluency of speech, comprehension ability, and repetition capacity [1, 21]. Impairment in repetition is also observed in Broca's aphasia, conductive aphasia, and global aphasia. However, the linguistic skills associated with repetition disorders differ from one another. Although repetition seems like a simple process of repeating heard words or non-word units, its neurolinguistic analysis is complex.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS.

A group of researchers led by Nazbanou Nozari studied cognitive processes in naming and repetition in aphasia [2, 541]. According to the research findings, in the two-stage model of lexical access, both semantic and phonological structure stages are involved in naming, but the semantic stage is not significant in repetition. Given the condition of recognizing the word to be repeated, the repetition process can occur in three ways: retrieving the output phonemes of the word from the lexicon (lexical route model), deriving output phonology directly from input phonology (non-lexical route model), or using both routes together (dual-route model). In examining the characteristics of sensory aphasia in the Uzbek language, patients' preserved ability to repeat was also investigated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Using the "Bilingual Aphasia Test," the following units were selected for patients to repeat. The first five units were non-meaningful units (*mat, chay, van, rob, bim*), six were two- and three-syllable meaningful words (*va'da, kitob, quyosh, bajarmoq, seminar, tarbiya*), and two were sentences (*Yigit qizni itardi; Yigit qizni ushladi*). Patients with sensory aphasia demonstrated the following results when performing repetition tasks.

Participants	Repetition of non-meaningful words	Repetition of meaningful words	Repetition of sentences
	5	6	2
NO	1	5	1
NI	2	5	1
MA	2	6	2
YF	2	4	0

Healthy participants performed the repetition task with 100% accuracy.

The results show that in sensory aphasia, meaningful words are repeated while the repetition of non-meaningful words is impaired. In sentence repetition, all participants except for MA were able to repeat only one sentence.

The experimental results are consistent with the following research findings on repetition impairment.

First, A. Luria also notes that in sensory aphasia, the impairment of word and sentence repetition can vary in degree [3, 187].

He also draws attention to the following aspects. The repetition of phonemes is limited due to severe impairment of phonemic hearing. Word repetition, however, can be somewhat preserved compared to phoneme repetition. If the patient says the word that needs to be repeated "automatically," they can perform well. It has been observed that if the patient tries to focus their attention on the sound analysis of the word, a search for the necessary phonemes and literal paraphasias emerges. For example, in Russian, a patient with sensory aphasia repeated the word "cat" as "dog," "violin" as "maestro," and "concert" as "performance."

This conclusion of A. Luria was confirmed by subsequent research.

In the aforementioned study led by Nazbanou Nazari, the differential sensitivity of naming and repetition skills to lexical search indices, which influence the phonological stage of lexical input, was determined. Initially, this work provides a neurological analysis of the naming and repetition process. Through the combined use of computer modeling and the case series method, the relationship between picture naming and auditory word repetition is investigated.

Computer modeling describes the naming process as follows.

In the first (semantic) stage, semantic nodes corresponding to the meaning of the named object are activated. The activation spreads to word nodes, with the activation of each receiving node determined by a linear activation function. From here, activation spreads further downwards but also flows to higher levels. The bidirectional spread of activation in the model makes it interactive, meaning that although there are two stages of processing, the stages are not fully modular, and each stage can and does influence the other. Evidence exists for such interactivity [4, 291].

In the activation model, random noise disturbs the activation of nodes at each time stage until a certain number of time stages have passed. This selects the most active node at the word level and completes the first step. The grammatical class of the target word constrains this selection, so if the target word should be a noun, only nouns can be selected at the word level. This property of the model is supported by the empirical finding that word errors (word substitutions, transpositions, guesses, or certainties) often correspond to the grammatical class of the target word they replace.

The second (phonological) step begins when the selected node at the word level receives an additional activation boost, which sends further activation through the network. At the end of the second stage, after the specified number of time stages has elapsed, the most active phoneme in each of the phoneme clusters is selected; the resulting combination of phonemes is considered the model's response.

During the repetition process, only the second (phonological) stage of the above model is activated.

We noted that 3 models of repetition have been proposed.

According to the lexical route model of repetition (phonological stage), it is noted that the repetition process overlaps with the second stage of the naming process.

According to the non-lexical route model, in repetition, the input phonology is directly mapped to the output phonology.

The repetition process is carried out with the involvement of phonological input and output nodes. Phonological input refers to the recognition of a word spoken for repetition, while phonological output refers to the verbal production of a word.

When comparing the naming and repetition processes in the study, it was observed that the frequency effect (speed of word recognition) is present in both cases.

Both meaningful words and non-meaningful words were used for repetition.

CONCLUSION.

Thus, we propose that the impairment of repetition skills in patients diagnosed with sensory aphasia is associated with damage to stage 2 (phonological output). The fact that patients were able to repeat meaningful words better than non-meaningful words supports the conclusion of the study led by N. Nozari, which suggests that the impairment of repetition ability in aphasia occurs as a result of equal reliance on both lexical and non-lexical routes.

Our results also align with the aforementioned studies.

Impairment of sentence repetition ability is one of the common conditions for patients with aphasia. In particular, one of the most important characteristics of conductive aphasia is the impaired ability to repeat others' speech (sentences) [7, 1157]. However, conductive aphasia is characterized by repetition disorder with relatively minor impairments in speech fluency and auditory comprehension.

Sensory aphasia results from damage to the superior temporal gyrus, while conductive aphasia arises from damage to the left arcuate fasciculus.

A. Luria notes that sentence repetition is easier than word and phoneme repetition, attributing this to the preservation of fluent syntagmatic speech in sensory aphasia.

As the scientist noted, speech message coding relies on paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations of language units. He supports R. Jakobson's hypothesis that all forms of speech disorders caused by local brain damage can be divided into two major classes: syntagmatic structural disorders and paradigmatic structural disorders. Damage to the posterior parts of the speech zones leads to the disruption of paradigmatic relations in speech, while syntagmatic speech is preserved. Conversely, damage to the anterior parts of the speech zones leads to a disruption of coherent, syntagmatically correct statements, but it is noted that this does not actually affect their paradigmatic (logical-grammatical) structure.

In the sentence repetition experiment, all participants except YF showed good results. It can be concluded that in these patients, the understanding of paradigmatic relations is impaired, while the understanding of syntagmatic relations is preserved, since the posterior region (the upper part of the temporal region) of the brain, rather than the anterior region, is affected.

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